

IPERION HS

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D 7.1 IPERION HS Training plan

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Abstract

The essential aim of Task 7.1 is to provide targeted training to develop suitably skilled individuals and to raise awareness amongst potential users of the benefits of using IPERION HS facilities. To this purpose, it has been decided to organize two Doctoral Summer Schools (HS-DSS) and two Training Camps (HS-TC) aimed at developing highly skilled professionals in the wider heritage research community, fostering cooperation between the academic community and heritage and research institutions.

Several online meetings have been organized in order to discuss and decide about the curricula and dates of the training activities. Given the uncertainty linked with the ongoing pandemic, it was decided that the first HS-DSS will be delivered virtually in July 2021, whereas the first HS-TC will be implemented in person in 2022 when it is expected the current travel restrictions will not be active anymore.

The first HS-DSS will mainly report on successful TNA and JRA achieved during the IPERION-CH project and will be addressed to a postgraduate, PhD and post-doc audience.

As the HS-TC are intended to be more interactive and more appropriate for learners with a mixed educational and professional background, it was decided to organise them in person in 2022 and 2023 respectively.

Both the HS-DSS and HS-TC will attract learners from a wide range of disciplines, so it is important to choose the subject materials and lecturers carefully.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
HS	Heritage Science
HS-DSS	IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School
HS-TC	IPERION HS Training Camp
JRA	Joint Research Activity
TNA	Transnational Access
CENIEH	Centro National de Investigacion sobre la Evolucion Humana
ITAM	Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics
UNIBO-M2ADL	University of Bologna – Microchemistry and Microscopy Art Diagnostic Laboratory

1. Introduction

The essential aim of Task 7.1 is to provide targeted training to develop suitably skilled individuals and to raise awareness amongst potential users of the benefits of using IPERION HS facilities. To this purpose, two Doctoral Summer Schools (HS-DSS) and two Training Camps (HS-TC) aimed at developing highly skilled professionals in the wider heritage research community, fostering cooperation between the academic community and heritage and research institutions, will be organized.

The HS-DSS and HS-TC activities will be branded and advertised as being part of the IPERION Academy for consistency with webinars and other IPERION HS training activities.

2. Work flowchart

Several online meetings have been held in order to discuss and decide about the curricula and dates of the training activities.

A possible work flowchart for the training activities has been proposed and discussed in collaboration with colleagues responsible for Task T8.2 (integrating access to training activities) and T8.3 (communication). It is structured as follows:

It has been decided to set up a communication environment for the implementation of on-line application submission system, in the form of a Google form hosted by the project website. The necessary data protection is described in the Data Management Plan (Deliverable 6.1).

IPERION HS

IPERION HS - Training: registration form

Fill the form in along with a short CV , before (date)

The name and photo associated with your Google account will be recorded when you upload files and submit this form. Not jstrioiva@gmail.com? [Switch account](#)

*** Required**

Email address *

Your email

PERSONAL DATA

Family / Last name *

Your answer

At the same time, the following scheme to be used for measuring the KPIs has been proposed and will be tested after the implementation of the first HS-DSS:

<i>Type</i>	<i>KPI</i>	<i>Value</i>
Training delivery	KPI1 (% provided training events vs planned events)	At Month 30 of the project 100
Support quality	KPI2 (% satisfaction in the top categories)	> 90%
Efficiency of TC user outreach	KPI3 (% submitted applications vs. available places)	> 90%
Quality of delivered training	KPI4 (% satisfaction in the top categories)	> 90%

3. IPERION-HS Doctoral Summer Schools (HS-DSS)

On the basis of the above mentioned work flowchart the following decisions concerning the first HS-DDS have been taken.

Steering Committee	All WP7 task leaders	Its role is to approve the scientific contents, the list of participants and lecturers of the HS-DDS
Topic	Excellence in heritage science for conservation and collection care research and access	The HS-DSS will allow the results achieved by TNA and JRA of both IPERION CH and IPERION HS projects, to be presented and discussed
Dates	13-16 July 2021	
Place	Completely taught on-line	
Organising institution	University of Bologna – Microchemistry and Microscopy Art Diagnostic Laboratory (M2ADL)	
Audience	Postgraduate, PhD and post-doctoral researchers involved in heritage science studies. Practitioners, in particular early career researchers	The lectures must adapt to an interdisciplinary plateau of learners by focusing more on problem solving than on the specific adopted scientific methods/technique
Structure	4 days: - 3 days of lectures (6 lectures each day = 18 lectures) - 2 half days for virtual study tours	
Advertisement/call for participants	February/March/April 2021	
Selection of participants	May 2021	
Language	English	All sessions will be conducted in English and therefore fluency in speaking and writing is essential.
Certificate of attendance	A certificate of attendance will be provided to all participants who attended the DDS for its whole duration	

We propose to organise the second HS-DDS in 2023 in order to allow more results achieved by the TNA and JRA of the IPERION-HS project to be disseminated.

4. IPERION-HS Training Camps (HS-TC)

As the HS-DSS, onsite Training Camps (HS-TC) are targeted at potential users of the IPERION-HS transnational access and will allow trainees to connect with practice. Through the use of innovative mobile and laboratory equipment, best practices and methodological approaches will be transferred directly to new potential users, to trainees, students and SMEs.

It has been decided to promote the involvement of new heritage science communities and, therefore, the subject of the first TC, organized by CENIEH, will be palaeoanthropology/palaeontology. The subject of the second TC, organized by ITAM, will be the built heritage.

The training camps are intended to be more interactive and more appropriate for learners with a mixed educational and professional background, and so will be delivered in person in 2022 and 2023 when it is expected that the current travel restrictions due to pandemic will not be active anymore.

A programme proposal for the first TC to be organized in 2022 has been discussed and approved as follows:

Steering Committee	All WP7 task leaders	Its role is to approve the scientific contents, the list of participants and lecturers of the HS-TC
Topic	Cutting-edge tools for materials characterization and dating applied to Paleontological and Paleoanthropological heritage	The HS-TC will allow the results achieved by TNA and JRA of both IPERION CH and IPERION HS projects, to be presented and discussed
Dates	2022 (dates to be defined)	
Place	Burgos (Spain) and Atapuerca (UNESCO site)	
Organising institution	Centro Nacional de Investigacion sobre la Evolucion Humana (CENIEH)	
Audience	The HS-TC is specifically aimed at young researchers/professionals in the field of Heritage science (either individuals or teams from public and/or private institutions) who are interested in approaching and developing studies on conservational and analytical problems.	All training activities must adapt to an interdisciplinary plateau of learners by focusing more on problem solving than on the specific adopted scientific methods/techniques
Structure	5 days	Hands-on experience, laboratory analyses, group projects, general lectures, fieldwork sessions
Advertisement/call for participants	February/March/April 2022	
Selection of participants	May 2022	
Language	English	All sessions will be conducted in English and therefore fluency in speaking and writing is essential.
Certificate of attendance	A certificate of attendance will be provided to all participants who attended the TC for its whole duration	In collaboration with WP8

5. User Feedback

A user satisfaction form will be set on-line by WP8, possibly addressing the following questions the learners will be asked to answer:

1	The publicity made by the partnership concerning the training camp (TC)
2	Practical information on how to apply on the project website and other communication channels
3	Contact with coordination team/s prior to beginning of TC for organizational purposes
4	Satisfaction with the professional level
5	Overall organization of the course
6	Facilities of the course
7	Satisfaction with the lectures
8	Usefulness of the TC for the advancement of your career
9	Interaction with the TC team/s during the course
10	Overall quality of the training provided
11	General fulfilment of expectations